

ReDi_Kid

Framework and objective

The objective is to obtain approximately 4,000 participants from 3rd and 4th grades across the Czech Republic, while reflecting regional, socio-economic, and settlement differences. We work with a frame of roughly 4,500 schools and use each school's capacity information.

Sampling unit and measure of size

The sampling unit is the school (cluster). In every sampled school we invite all pupils in 3rd and 4th grades (take-all).

To align selection probabilities with the expected number of participants, we define the measure of size "M" as "school capacity divided by 9". This comes from two ninths of capacity corresponding to 3rd and 4th grades and an assumed participation rate of about 50 percent. In other words: $M = \text{Capacity} \div 9$ and represents the expected number of participants at the school.

Stratification

To ensure representativeness, we stratify the frame by three dimensions:

- Region (KOD_KRAJ),
- SES (0 = lower, 1 = higher),
- Municipality status (village / town / statutory city).

We include municipality status because settlement type is related to infrastructure availability, travel behaviour, and likelihood of participation.

Allocation and number of schools per stratum

We first allocate the overall target of ~4,000 expected participants proportionally across strata. Each stratum receives a share proportional to the sum of "M" in that stratum relative to the overall sum of "M" in the frame.

To determine the number of schools in a stratum, we estimate the typical size of a selected school in that stratum as "sum of M squared divided by sum of M". The stratum's school count is then roughly "allocated participants in the stratum divided by this typical size", rounded to an integer. We then make

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small adjustments (adding or removing one school in a few strata) so that the realised total expected participants is as close as possible to 4,000.

Selection procedure (systematic PPS)

Within every stratum we run a systematic Probability-Proportional-to-Size (PPS) sample. We use a random start and an interval equal to “sum of M in the stratum divided by the stratum’s number of schools”. This yields, for each school, a selection probability roughly equal to “stratum school count times the school’s M divided by the stratum’s sum of M”. Larger schools (higher M) therefore have a higher chance to be selected, which is fair given our goal to reach the target number of participants.

Child inclusion (take-all)

In sampled schools we invite all pupils in 3rd and 4th grades. This reduces operational complexity (no within-school subsampling) and keeps weighting simple.

Weighting and analysis

The base weight for invited children in a sampled school equals the inverse of the school’s selection probability (that is, 1 divided by the school’s selection probability). Because we use take-all within schools, the child’s weight is the same as the school’s weight.

In analysis we recommend adding a non-response adjustment within reasonably homogeneous groups (e.g., region × SES × municipality status, or by school) and then calibrating/post-stratifying the final weights to known margins (numbers of pupils in 3rd–4th grades by region/SES/status, if available). This stabilises estimates against potential differences in participation.

Why this design

- Representativeness across contexts: stratifying by region, SES, and municipality status controls key sources of variability (regional differences, socio-economic profile, settlement type).
- Efficiency and fairness: PPS based on expected participants ($\text{Capacity} \div 9$) ensures larger schools have a higher probability to be sampled, while each child within a stratum has roughly comparable chances (after accounting for participation).

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- Fieldwork simplicity: take-all in 3rd–4th grades minimises on-site burden and simplifies communication with schools.
- Control of achieved sample size: proportional allocation across “M” and minor adjustments to stratum school counts let us target ~4,000 expected participants without overshooting or undershooting.
- Transparency and reproducibility: systematic PPS with a random start is a standard, well-documented procedure.

Note on “empty” combinations

Because we can have up to 84 potential strata (14 regions × 2 SES × 3 municipality statuses) and we sample roughly 72 schools, it is not possible to include at least one school in every possible combination. Small strata may round down to zero schools. If guaranteed presence is required (e.g., at least one school in every region, or in every region × SES), we can enforce minimum quotas and re-distribute the remainder so that the overall target (~4,000) is preserved.

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